

Ground State Quantum Oscillator Density as an Entropy Maximum

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 29, 2022

Classical statistical mechanical density maximizes entropy subject to constraints i.e. one has the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution $P(x)P(p)$ proportional to $\exp(-pp/2mT - V(x)/T)$. Quantum mechanics is also a statistical theory, but it is not based on the maximization of entropy. Rather it is based on a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ where $W(x)$ = wavefunction = $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ such that: $\sum_p pp/2m P(p/x) + V(x) = E$ (bound states). As a result, it has classical densities $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$, but these in general do not maximize entropy and so do not match the MB distribution. There is a special case, however, namely the ground state oscillator for which the quantum mechanical results $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ are both Gaussians. It is shown in (1) that for a fixed variance, a Gaussian maximizes entropy. Thus, the MB scenario must be a Gaussian for an oscillator as it is, but the quantum result is also a Gaussian and so matches the classical statistical mechanical result. In this note, we show that the time-independent Schrodinger equation collapses to the equality situation in Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, suggesting that the solution also represents maximum entropy.

Gaussian as Maximum Entropy for a Given Variance

Consider a given standard deviation b . As stated in (1), a Gaussian distribution yields the maximum Shannon's entropy subject to b a fixed standard deviation i.e.

$$\text{Maximize } - \int dx d(x) \ln(d(x)) + c_1 \int dx xx d(x) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Here } \langle x \rangle = 0 \quad \text{Then: } d(x) = 1/\sqrt{2\pi b^2} \exp(-xx/2bb) \quad ((2))$$

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution with no potential follows from maximizing entropy subject to constant energy:

$$\text{Maximize } - \int dp d(p) \ln(d(p)) + c_1 \int dp pp/2m d(p) \quad \text{to obtain}$$

$d(p)$ proportional to $\exp(-pp/2mT)$ ((3)) Thus given $mT =$ variance, a Gaussian (MB) is the maximum entropy solution. If a potential $V(x)$ is present, the result is:

$$d(p,x) \text{ proportional to } \exp(-pp/2mT - V(x)/T)$$

For an oscillator, one has a product of Gaussians i.e. a maximum distribution for both x and p for their respective standard deviations.

Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics is a statistical theory which seems to be based on a special condition, namely that a free particle is represented by a "special" probability of $\exp(ipx)$. If a potential $V(x)$ is present it creates an ensemble of free particle special probabilities i.e. $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. The fundamental condition is that the average energy at each x (like T in classical statistical mechanics) must be the constant $E = \text{energy}$. Thus:

$$\left\{ \sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3))$$

No considerations have been given to entropy (unless one argues that the form $\exp(ipx)$ is based on entropy considerations). The ensemble $W(x)$, however, is not.

((3)) is equivalent to the time-independent Schrodinger equation and yields results for $W(x)$ and $a(p)$. It may be shown that classical probabilities $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ also exist for the quantum situation and are given by:

$$P(x) = W(x)W(x) \text{ bound states} \quad \text{and} \quad P(p) = a(p)a(p) \quad ((4))$$

$P(x)$ and $P(p)$ do not in general match the MB distribution nor would one expect them to because they are not based on the maximization of entropy subject to constraints.

There is a special case, namely the solution of the ground state oscillator for which $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ are both Gaussians i.e. $W(x)$ is proportional to $\exp(-a.5 xx)$ and $a(p) = \exp(-.5 pp/a)$ where a is proportional to \sqrt{km} , k being the spring constant.

Oscillator Ground State

Given that the ground state oscillator $P(x) = C_1 \exp(-axx)$ and $P(p) = C_2 \exp(-pp/a)$ these distributions represent maximum entropy for a fixed standard deviation. This is the same situation as the classical statistical mechanical oscillator. No maximization of entropy, however, has been applied, so how does this result arise?

In (1) it is shown that Heisenberg's uncertainty principle equality limit

$$\sqrt{\text{Var}(x)} \sqrt{\text{Var}(p)} = \hbar/2 \quad ((5))$$

follows from using Gaussians which represent maximum entropy. In particular (1) shows that:

$H(x) = \text{Shannon's entropy} = \ln(2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot e \cdot b)$ where b is the standard deviation of x .

(This follows from using a Gaussian $d(x) = 1/\sqrt{2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot b \cdot b} \exp(-xx/2bb)$ in Shannon's entropy form.)

Using the entropic uncertainty form (1):

$H(p)+H(x) = \ln(e^{3.14})$ where e means maximum entropies are used i.e. Gaussian distributions.

Thus: $\ln[2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot e \cdot b(x)] \ln[2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot e \cdot b(p)] = \ln(e^{3.14})$ or $b(x)b(p) = .5$ with \hbar as 1 ((6))

This is the equality limit of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. Thus to prove maximum entropy (i.e. Gaussians) we suggest that for quantum mechanics one needs to show one has $b(p)b(x) = \text{standard deviation}(p) \text{ standard deviation}(x) = \text{constant}$ by using the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

For an oscillator ground state

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + .5kx^2 W(x) = \hbar \omega \cdot .5 W(x) \quad ((7))$$

Multiplying by $W(x)$ and integrating yields:

$$-1/2m \int W(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + .5k \text{Var}(x) = \hbar \omega \cdot .5 \quad ((8))$$

In (2) it is suggested that $\langle a(p)|a(p) \rangle = \langle g(x)|g(x) \rangle$ where $g(x) = -i \frac{d}{dx} W(x)$

$$\text{Thus } ((8)) \text{ is: } .5/m \text{Var}(p) + .5k \text{Var}(x) = \hbar \omega \cdot .5 \quad ((9))$$

Average kinetic energy and average potential energy, however, are the same so: $1/m \text{Var}(p) = .5\hbar \omega$ and $k\text{Var}(x) = .5 \hbar \omega$ where $\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$ Thus:

$$\sqrt{\text{Var}(p)\text{Var}(x)} = .5\hbar \sqrt{m/k} \omega = .5 \hbar \omega \quad ((10))$$

This is the limit of the Heisenberg uncertainty principle based on a distribution which maximizes entropy. This shows how a quantum wavefunction is related to the maximum entropy result.

Alternatively, one may note that $W(x)$ is proportional to $\exp(-.5ax^2)$ and $a(p)$ is proportional to $\exp(-.5pp/a)$. This solution of the Schrodinger equation happens to also represent maximum entropy for given variances.

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) states that the equality in the Heisenberg momentum-x uncertainty relationship pertains to maximum entropy distributions for p and x , namely Gaussian distributions. This result holds for the oscillator Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, but classical statistical mechanics is known to be linked to maximization of entropy. Quantum mechanics is not. For the ground state of an oscillator, however, $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ are both Gaussians suggesting maximum entropy distributions for given variances. In this note we show that the time-independent Schrodinger for the ground state oscillator is a sum of $C1 \text{Var}(x) + C2\text{Var}(p)$, but $C1\text{Var}(x)=C2\text{Var}(p)$ from which it follows that the standard deviation product equals

Heisenberg's limit which is known to represent maximum entropy distributions (i.e. Gaussians). Thus the ground state oscillator solution not only satisfies the Schrodinger equation, but produces $W(x)$, $a(p)$ as solutions which maximize entropy and so match the classical statistical mechanical MB result.

References

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